

CARBON NANODOTS AS LIGHT-ACTIVATED OXIDASE NANOZYME FOR ECO-FRIENDLY LEACHING OF COPPER FROM SCRAP

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ABSTRACT. The copper is the second largest strategic raw material. Since there is a huge gap between copper production and consumption, a green and eco-sustainable recycling technology is necessary that is able to process the copper from secondary sources of waste and scraps. Here we demonstrate the photo-oxidising properties of pyrrolic nitrogen-dominated carbon nanodots as eco-friendly and powerful oxidase-mimicking nanozyme for leaching of copper from metal scrap under irradiation with either ultraviolet or natural sun light (average intensity of 59 000 lux). The ultra-small nanoparticles with diameter < 5 nm were prepared by 600 W microwave-assisted pyrolysis, which might be considered as energy efficient synthetic method. The developed strategy enables to dissolve Cu metal at neutral pH range (between 5.1 – 8.3) and it might break the pH limitation for recycling of copper in the conventional chemical methods, where toxic and corrosive substances are used. The obtained yield was about 5 %, which is still not satisfactory for practical application in recycle technology. Nevertheless, according to our knowledge there is not any other reported photosensitizer nanozyme, which is capable to induce oxidation and dissolving of copper under natural light irradiation of neutral leaching solution.

Key words: oxidase-mimicking nanozyme, carbon nanodots, copper leaching

Introduction

The functional nanomaterials with enzyme-mimicking properties, also known as "artificial enzymes" or nanozymes, are a stimulating branch of biomimetics, which have attracted considerable attention due to their potential application as alternative catalysts of natural enzymes (Zhang et al., 2021). Among them the carbon-based nanomaterials have generated enormous scientific excitement because of the higher stability and lower cost than those of protein enzymes (Wang et al., 2021). Other reasons are also the diversified structural modulations and opportunity to be used as a platform for passivation, chemical modification and bioconjugation, as well as the absence of metal atoms or ions in their chemical contents (Jin et al., 2021). In that respect, the ultra-small pyrrolic nitrogen-dominated carbon nanodots (C-dots) were found to perform an efficient both peroxidase and oxidase-mimicking activity (Loukanov et al., 2022), which can be modulated by either pre-engineering of their surface structures or introducing a photo-regulated host-guest reaction (Lv et al., 2018). These metal-free materials are quasi-spherical nanoparticles that comprise amorphous nanocrystalline cores with a diameter between 1 – 5 nm (Wei et al., 2020). The oxidase-mimicking properties of nitrogen-doped C-dots have been systematically investigated under ultraviolet and visible (UV-VIS) irradiation and the nanoparticles were proved to exhibit catalytic ability close to that of their natural counterpart (Garg and Bisht, 2016). Therefore, the ultra-small C-dots can be classified as light-activated oxidase nanozymes (Loukanov et al., 2022). In fact, during the photo-catalytic process, reactive oxygen species are generated (Lv et al., 2018). C-dots catalytic activity is irrelevant to any cation-related binding sites and many references report that the nanozyme is able to produce reactive singlet oxygen (Zhang et al., 2019). Particularly interesting is the ability of C-dots to mimic oxidase-like activity even at neutral condition, and thus they break the acidic pH limitations that are characteristic for most artificial nanozymes (Yuxin et al., 2022). The intrinsic nanozyme activity

of C-dots opens an opportunity for their utilisation as versatile and environmentally friendly catalysts in numerous applications in ecology and green biotechnology, as well as the possibility to be applied for metal leaching from scrap in the recycling technology. The copper waste from electric and electronic equipment is certainly one of the common metals that might be recycled repeatedly and reused again (Işildar et al., 2019). In that respect, many eco-friendly and sustainable technologies have been investigated for Cu metal recovery without the use or release of volatile, toxic, or chemically dangerous substances (Needhidasan et al., 2014). In some of them the use of corrosive and oxidant acidic leaching solution remains still a challenge, which is hard to overcome (Babu et al., 2007).

Here we demonstrate the dissolving of metal copper in leaching solution with pH-values around neutral point by employing C-dots as photo-activated oxidase nanozyme. The proposed strategy might break the pH acidic limitations for recycling of copper in the conventional wet chemistry methods. In our experiments C-dots were obtained from citric acid and ethylene diamine via the microwave-assisted pyrolysis, which is a well-studied "Bottom-up" approach (Zhai et al., 2012). Next, ligand-stabilised EDTA-Mn (III) was introduced into the reaction mixture as a mediator that significantly enhances the efficiency of electron transfer in the process (Webb et al., 2005), and thus enhances the rate of copper oxidation and leaching. In the proposed strategy, the formed redox potential of the pair Mn (II) / Mn (III) is 1.54 V, which was strong enough to induce spontaneous reaction of oxidation between manganese (III) ions and Cu⁰ from the metal scrap.

Experimental Procedures

Chemicals and instrumentation

The chemicals used in the experimental section were as follows: ethylenediamine or EDA, anhydrous, NH₂CH₂CH₂NH₂, citric acid, C₆H₈O₇ (purchased from Kanto Chemical Co. Inc.), manganese (II) sulphate pentahydrate, MnSO₄·5H₂O

(purchased from Wako), 4H (EDTA, free acid) or ethylenediamine-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid, $C_{10}H_{16}N_2O_8$ (purchased from Dojindo, Japan). The water was purified by an Autopure WD 500 (Yamato Science, Tokyo, Japan) through Millipath® 40, Millipore 0.22 μm . A thin metal copper plate with a size of 2 x 11 cm (5.4711 g in weight) was used as a model scrap material. For preparation of reaction solutions were used an analytical balance ITX120, pH-meter AS800 (AXEL, As One, Japan) and magnetic stirrer MS7-H550-S (DLAB, Scientific, Inc., USA). The samples were irradiated with natural sun light and UV-light with irradiation wavelength of 365 nm (Handy UV-Lamp, 100 V, 50/60 Hz, As One, Japan). The absorbance spectra were measured in a quartz cell by an analytical UV-VIS Jasco spectrophotometer (model № V-570). The change of the colour intensity of the copper leaching concentrate solution was measured periodically at 600 nm by AP-120 photoelectric colorimeter (APEL Co., Ltd., Japan).

Nanoparticle size distribution was determined using dynamic light scattering (DLS, Zetasizer Nano ZS).

Synthesis of oxidase nanozyme

The carbon nanoparticles used in the reported study were prepared via 600 W microwave-assisted pyrolysis of 1 g citric acid and 200 μL ethylenediamine, dissolved into 10 mL of deionised water (Toshev and Loukanov, 2020).

Preparation of copper leaching concentrate solution

The obtained nanomaterials were re-suspended into 150 mL aqueous solution of 0.01 M MnSO_4 . The obtained pH was 2.46. After that 0.5 g EDTA was added into the suspension under energetic mixing by magnetic stirrer, but it remains

undissolved at room temperature. The reaction solution was slowly neutralised to pH = 5.1 by dropwise adding of 1.0 M NaOH. At that pH value, all amount of EDTA was well dissolved and the solution turned to transparent. Then, the metal copper plate was inserted on the bottom of the reaction vessel (under the solution surface) and illuminated by either (i) UV-lamp or (ii) the natural sun light (with average intensity of 59 300 Lux). In the second case, the reaction vessel was kept for five days on the laboratory bench close to the window and the change of solution colour was monitored by the absorbance spectrophotometer or photoelectric colorimeter. During that period there was a gradual change in the colour of the leaching concentrate solution as follows - from light yellow to deep green-blue (after 1 week) and finally to dark-green (after 6 weeks). The solution pH also increased from 5.1 to 7.3 (after 1 week) and to 8.3 (after 6 weeks). At the end of each leaching reaction, the change in weight of the copper metal plate was measured.

Results and Discussion

Nanozyme characterisation

The synthesised nanoparticles are characterised with good solubility in aqueous solution due to the abundance of hydrophilic groups on their surface as carboxyl, amino, hydroxyl, etc. When dispersed into water the obtained solution colour is light yellow as shown on Figure 1A (left side). The nanozyme exhibits absorbance, mainly in the near UV-region with tail of decreasing intensity in the visual range until 600 nm (Figure 1B).

Fig. 1. Spectrophotometric analysis of the photo-oxidation catalytic leaching of copper from the metal scrap. (A) Photograph taken of the initial leaching solution before the oxidation (left, yellow colour) and after oxidation (right, deep green-blue) of the metal plate. Absorbance spectra of (B) initial leaching solution and (C) the concentrated solution which contained leached copper ions

Only two peaks in the UV region were registered, which are located at 256-270 nm and 350-360 nm. They are assigned to the C=C $\pi-\pi^*$ and C=O $n-\pi^*$ transitions, respectively. Under irradiation with UV-lamp, (365 nm irradiation wavelength) the leaching solution shows bright-blue photoluminescence (PL). PL emission peak is located at 470 nm, and it can gradually shift to longer wavelength with the increase of the excitation wavelength, i.e., the carbon nanoparticles exhibit excitation-dependent PL behaviour in the visual range. Since the absorbance intensity is decreasing toward longer wavelengths, the emission intensity is naturally diminishing too. This suggests that the photosensitising reaction with highest yield of singlet oxygen production must be achieved under illumination with ultraviolet irradiation. In the case of visible light the yield significantly decreased, and without light irradiation (dark mode) the nanozyme cannot act as photosensitiser (Zhang et al., 2019), and therefore the copper cannot be oxidised.

Leaching of copper metal

Under optimised conditions (pH 5.1 – 8.3, ambient temperature and sun irradiation with average intensity of 60 000 Lux) the nanozyme exhibits catalytic activity to leach copper metal through singlet oxygen production and use of Mn(III) ions as a mediator. The UV-VIS spectrum of the leaching solution at neutral pH before the reaction of oxidation is shown in Figure 1B. As it is shown with an arrow, no absorbance peak is registered in the visible or near infrared (NIR) range of the spectrum. Such absorbance peak appears around 710 - 730 nm (as shown on Figure 1C) after performing the photo-oxidation reaction with nanozyme and leaching copper in the solution. Thus, further deep green-blue colour was observed, which is assigned to the oxidised Cu(II) metal ions.

The formation of visual deep green-blue colour, as shown on Figure 1A (right side) with absorbance maximum in the VIS and NIR range illustrated the process of slow dissolving of copper metal as Cu^{2+} ions (within 6 weeks as shown with the yellow arrow on Figure 1C). Most of them are existing as Cu-EDTA complex at neutral pH.

A better comparison of the absorbance spectra of the initial leaching solution (solid yellow line as control experiment) and the copper oxidation concentrate (dotted blue line) is presented on Figure 2.

As shown, the absorbance peaks of both spectra in UV range are a little shifted (Figure 2A). If the nanozyme is mixed with MnSO_4 and EDTA, no peak is observed in the NIR region between 600 – 900 nm (Figure 2B, solid yellow line).

Without nanozyme, again no colour change (no peak) was observed during the treatment of copper with EDTA and Mn(II) under light illumination. Nevertheless, when the leaching solution in the presence of the nanozyme was subject to irradiation with natural sun light within five days, the copper metal plate was dissolved and a peak with maximum absorption approximately 730-740 nm appeared (Figure 2B, dotted blue line). The experimental data revealed that the photo-oxidation reaction effects the absorbance of nanozyme because its peak is shifted from 352 nm to 348 nm (after 1 week) and it is not observable after 6 weeks.

From the spectrum intensity of Figure 2B the amount of leached Cu(II) ions in solution could also be determined via stoichiometry, but the calculated concentration is not equal to

Fig. 2. Absorbance spectra of (A) initial solution, and (B) concentrated leaching solution in VIS and near infrared range

the total amount of leached copper, because some of the Cu exists as black deposited oxides on the metal surface. The most accurate way to measure the amount of leached copper was by weight measurement of the metal plate before and after the reaction. All data confirmed that the plate dissolved, but the oxidation speed was slow. For about five days we found a reduction in weight from 5.5 g to 5.4 g (~ 2.0 % yield), and after 6 weeks to 5.2 g (~ 5.0 % yield). From a practical point of view, this leaching speed is not yet appropriate for application of the nanozyme in the recycling technology, but the method is still in its infancy.

Reaction mechanism

Because the main focus of reported study was the light-activated catalysis, we turned our attention to understanding the reaction mechanism as shown in the scheme on Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of the nanozyme photo-oxidase activity at neutral pH and demonstration of the reaction mechanism, including the participation of Mn(II)/Mn(III) redox pair as ligand-stabilised mediator and oxidant of copper metal

Under light irradiation the singlet oxygen ($^1\Delta_g$ or $^1\text{O}_2$) is produced from the nanozyme reacting with ground state oxygen ($^3\Sigma_g^-$ or $^3\text{O}_2$).

The short phosphorescence lifetime of $^1\text{O}_2$ is the reason for its short migration distance and fast deactivation to the ground triplet state.

This problem was solved in our experiments by adding of a ligand-stabilised mediator that can diffuse for a longer time.

The dissolved Mn(II) being oxidised to Mn(III) by $^1\text{O}_2$, so the formed ions are stabilised by EDTA and further fulfil their role as a mediator for copper leaching. Mn(II) is oxidised to Mn(III) by the dissolved singlet oxygen and the reaction rate was enhanced by adding of EDTA (Zhang et al., 2019).

We confirmed that the dissolved Mn(II) itself does not react with Cu^0 without light at neutral pH. Therefore, the role of Mn(II) is only to produce Mn(III), which is a stronger oxidiser and reacts with copper as a mediator. Two reactions might occur:

as well as

The forming of black precipitation coverage on the metal surface, as shown on the photo (Figure 4), indicates a reaction of oxidation that results in copper oxide. This reaction might occur between the dissolved cations or directly between the activated oxygen and the metal surface.

Fig. 4. Photo of the copper plate, which is coated with a black thin layer of copper oxide

or

During the process of copper oxidation and leaching the solution pH is rising from 5.1 to 8.3. This indicated that hydroxyl anions were released and/or reaction of neutralisation between the copper oxide and EDTA occurred:

Thermodynamic calculations

The calculations related to the overall thermodynamically favourable reaction between manganese and copper in the leaching solution, i.e. copper oxidation by Mn(III), are presented below:

For this reaction the number of moles of electrons transferred per mole is $z = 2$.

Oxidation process:

Reduction process:

The standard cell potential (E°_{cell}) at 298 K is:

$$E^\circ_{\text{cell}} = [E^\circ_{\text{red.}}] - [E^\circ_{\text{ox.}}] = 1.54 \text{ V} - 0.34 \text{ V} = 1.20 \text{ V}$$

The corresponding Gibbs energy is:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -zFE^\circ_{\text{cell}} = -2 \times 96485 \times 1.20 = -231564 \text{ J}$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -232 \text{ kJ per mole of reaction}$$

The equilibrium constant K is:

$$\ln K = -(\Delta G^\circ/RT) = -(-232 / 8.314 \times 10^{-3} \times 298) = 93.66$$

$$K = 4.7 \times 10^{40}$$

Therefore, the reaction between the catalytically produced Mn(III) and $\text{Cu}_{(s)}$ is spontaneous at ambient temperature, because the value of E°_{cell} is positive, ΔG° is negative and $K \gg 1$. As confirmed previously, Mn(II) can be oxidised to Mn(III) by the dissolved oxygen which is converted to $^1\text{O}_2$. The presence of singlet oxygen was confirmed in our previous report by its phosphorescence emission at 1275 nm (Toshev et al., 2020). Based on the thermodynamical calculations we have assumed that the catalytically produced Mn(III) is responsible for the oxidation of copper metal at pH = 5.1 – 7.3 (neutral conditions). In general, Mn(III) ions are unstable in aqueous solution and that was the reason to be stabilised by EDTA ligands. Under illumination with natural sun light the colour of the leaching solution changes from yellow to blue within few days. By using UV-lamp the result might be achieved even for shorter time.

Conclusion

In this report the photo-catalytic performance of N-doped C-dots as an oxidase-mimicking nanozyme to leach copper was investigated. To the best of our knowledge there is no any other nanozyme-induced oxidation of copper at neutral pH under natural sun light irradiation. The obtained results demonstrated that the leaching speed was too slow and not appropriate yet for the nanozyme application in the recycling technology. Nevertheless, the method is still in its infancy and deserves further studies.

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